

Effective prevention of atopic dermatitis by ingestion of kestose compared with maltose in high-risk neonates: a single-center, randomized, double-blinded, parallel, two-group, phase II trial

Short Title: Kestose intake for prevention of atopic dermatitis in Tokyo (KITY study)

Trial Protocol

Version 1.4

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ESTABLISHMENT AND AMENDMENT

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1.1	April 15, 2022	Mayako Saito-Abe	Revision of the items for which information was collected
1.2	February 6, 2023	Mayako Saito-Abe	The amount of blood revised, Revision of the study schedule
1.3	January 12, 2024	Mayako Saito-Abe	Extension of the study duration, Addition of allowable period of start day of intervention and switching day for frequency and dose of intervention, Partial changes to adherence definition
1.4	June 17, 2024	Kenji Toyokuni	Revision of principal investigator and sub-investigator

1.	Matters concerning the implementation system of clinical research	6
1.1.	Medical institution and principal investigator	6
1.2.	Research collaborator	6
1.3.	Research administration and coordination and management staff	6
1.4.	Statistical analysis manager	7
1.5.	Assignment responsible person	7
1.6.	Data center and data management manager	7
1.7.	Research and development planning support officer	7
1.8.	Monitoring officer	7
1.9.	Chief auditor	7
1.10.	Efficacy and safety evaluation committee member	8
1.11.	Kestose, maltose donor	8
1.12.	Analysis of intestinal flora in feces	8
1.13.	Treg measurement	8
1.14.	Total IgE , specific IgE , SCCA2 measurement	8
2.	Matters related to the background of the study	8
2.1.	Background	8
2.2.	Outline of Pharmaceuticals	10
3.	Purpose	12
4.	Matters related to the content of the study	12
4.1.	Phase of the study	12
4.2.	Sample size	12
4.3.	Study design	12
5.	Eligibility	13
5.1.	Inclusion criteria	13
5.2.	Exclusion criteria	13
5.3.	Discontinuation of treatment	14
5.4.	Discontinuation of the study	14
6.	Study procedures	15
6.1.	Registration	15
6.2.	Randomization and stratification	15
6.3.	Blinding	15
6.4.	Disclosure of allocation in case of emergency	15
6.5.	Study intervention	16
6.6.	Study assessments	17
7.	Efficacy endpoints	21
7.1.	Primary endpoint	21

7.2.	Secondary endpoints	21	
8.	Safety assessment.....	21	
8.1.	Safety endpoints	21	
8.2.	Reporting of illness and response to serious illness	22	
9.	Statistical analyses.....	22	
9.1.	Analysis set.....	22	
9.2.	Significance level	23	
9.3.	Analysis methods.....	23	
9.3.1.	Summary of background information	23	
9.3.2.	Analysis of primary endpoints	23	
9.3.3.	Analysis of secondary endpoints.....	24	
9.3.4.	Analysis of safety endpoints.....	24	
9.4.	Interim analysis	24	
9.5.	Procedure for modifying the statistical analysis plan	24	
10.	Access to original documents and other materials	24	
10.1.	Scope of source documents	24	
10.2.	Guarantee of direct access to source documents.....	24	
11.	Quality control and quality assurance	24	
11.1.	Monitoring.....	24	
11.2.	Audit.....	24	
11.3.	Effectiveness and safety evaluation committee	25	
12.	Ethical considerations.....	25	
12.1.	Rules to be observed	25	
12.2.	Handling of personal information	25	
12.3.	Measures to minimize the benefits and burdens and anticipated risks to the participants	26	
13.	Handling and storage of records.....	26	
13.1.	Handling and storage of documents	26	
13.2.	Storage of samples, etc., and use of samples, etc., by other institutions, etc.	26	
13.3.	Data collection methods.....	27	
14.	Payment of money and compensation for the conduct of clinical research	27	
14.1.	Funding sources and financial offices (matters relating to conflicts of interest)	27	
14.2.	Cost related to the research.....	27	
14.3.	Compensation for damage to health	27	
15.	Publication policy and attribution of productions	28	
16.	Duration of clinical research.....	28	
17.	Explanation to and consent of clinical research participants	28	

17.1. Preparation and revision of explanatory documents and consent forms..	28
17.2. Informed consent	28
17.3. Informed assent	30
17.4. Withdrawal of consent.....	30
18. Other matters necessary for the proper implementation of clinical research	30
18.1. Contents and methods of reporting to the administrator of the IMPLEMENTING medical institution	30
18.1.1. Reports from researchers, etc.....	30
18.1.2. Reports from the principal investigator.....	30
18.1.3. Report from the individual in charge of the audit	31
18.2. Changes to research protocols	31
18.2.1. Amendments to the research protocol	31
18.2.2. Revisions to the research protocol	32
18.2.3. Explanation to participants and provision of consent following changes to the research protocol	32
18.3. Consultation.....	33
18.4. References	33
18.5. Attachments.....	34

Term Definition

Study intervention	Ingestion of test sugar (kestose) or control sugar (maltose)
Study intervention period	From the start date of test sugar and control sugar intake until 20 weeks of age (Visit 4) or the date of discontinuation
Test period	From the date of registration until the 20th week of life or until the date of discontinuation

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AD	Atopic Dermatitis
CI	Confidence Interval
EASI	Eczema Area and Severity Index
EDC	Electronic Data Capture
eCRF	Electronic Case Report Form
IgE	Immunoglobulin E
IRB	Institutional Review Board
ITT	Intention-to-Treat
POEM	Participant-Oriented Eczema Measure
SCH	Stratum corneum hydration
TEWL	Transdermal Water Loss

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2. Matters related to the background of the study

2.1. Background

AD is a disease characterized by itchy eczema with repeated flares. Most individuals affected by AD have a "predisposition to atopy" (family history and predisposition to immunoglobulin E [IgE] antibody production)¹). Itching and the chronic and recurrent course of AD result in a significant decrease in quality of life. This process triggers the allergic march, a phenomenon in which various allergic diseases develop throughout life after sensitization to allergens during infancy ¹). Among atopic predispositions, family history of AD has a significant influence. Approximately 70% of participants with AD have a family history of AD ²), and it has been reported that the risk of developing AD is 2–3 and 3–6 times higher when one and both parents have AD, respectively ³). It is also well established that AD in a sibling or one parent result in a similar risk of developing the disease in childhood ⁴).

According to an epidemiological study conducted between 1994 and 1996 by the International Study of Asthma and

Allergies in Childhood, which examined the prevalence of AD worldwide, the prevalence of AD in children aged 6–7 years was 7.3% 5). Based on an analysis of 14 publications on the prevalence of AD in Japan over a 10-year period (1992–2002), the prevalence rates by age ranged 6–32% in infants, 5–27% in young children, 5–15% in school children, and 5–9% in university students; notably, the rate exhibited a decreasing trend with age 6). In addition, data from the growth cohort showed that 32.3% of 1,157 children had been diagnosed with AD at least once by the age of 9 years 7). The high likelihood of percutaneous antigen sensitization in individuals with AD is becoming a well-established concept . In addition, it is currently recognized that worsening eczema can be a cause of various allergic diseases 8). Our research group conducted a prospective cohort study of newborns, revealing that infant eczema precedes allergic march at 1 month of age 9). We also reported that treatment of AD decreases serum IgE, which indicates allergic disposition 10). Based on the above evidence, it was inferred that prevention of the onset of AD by skin care at an earlier stage is important for the prevention of allergic diseases later in childhood.

We conducted a clinical trial to investigate whether skin care before the appearance of eczema, including the application of moisturizers and barrier function aids, can prevent the development of AD in high-risk newborns 11). A previous study compared a group that received moisturizer 2e (Doe; Shiseido, Tokyo, Japan) at least once daily from birth with a group that received vaseline as needed. The results showed that the cumulative incidence of AD at 32 weeks after birth was significantly lower in the group receiving 2e versus that receiving Vaseline (hazard ratio: 0.48; 95% confidence interval [CI]: 0.27–0.86) (Figure 1). However, application of moisturizers from birth did not completely prevent AD, and approximately 40% of the children developed AD by 32 weeks of age.

In recent years, few reports on the prevention of allergic diseases by prebiotics have been published. Grüber et al. conducted a clinical trial to examine whether oligosaccharide intake can prevent AD in high-risk newborns with a family history of allergic diseases 12). A study compared a group that received artificial milk containing oligosaccharides from birth with another that received artificial milk containing placebo or breast milk. The findings showed that the cumulative incidence of AD by 1 year of age was 5.7%, 9.7%, and 7.3% in the intervention, placebo, and breast milk groups, respectively. As demonstrated, the incidence of AD was lower in the intervention group. Comparison of the intervention and placebo groups revealed that the cumulative incidence of AD was significantly lower in the intervention group ($P=0.039$; hazard ratio: 0.560; 95% CI: 0.323–0.971) (Figure 2).

Figure 1

In a systematic review published in 2017, there were no statistically significant findings with regard to the effectiveness of prebiotics in preventing the development of eczema, though the observed trend was promising (Figure 3)13).

Among prebiotics, we focused on kestose in this study. Kestose is a trisaccharide consisting of the sucrose β -1,1-glycoside bonded to the sucrose fructose. This prebiotic increases the abundance of butyrate-producing bacteria in the intestine, thereby resulting in higher levels of butyrate in this organ. Butyrate induces regulatory T cell differentiation and suppresses allergic diseases. Shibata et al. reported the therapeutic effect of kestose on AD in 30 children with AD aged < 3 years. By comparing the SCORing Atopic Dermatitis index (SCORAD) after 12 weeks of daily intake of kestose with that of maltose, the investigators demonstrated that AD was significantly improved in the kestose group (19.5) versus the maltose group (37.5) ($P < 0.001$)14). However, there have been no previous reports on the preventive effect of kestose on AD.

Figure 2

Figure 3

(A) Eczema

2.2. Outline of Pharmaceuticals

The kestose and maltose used in this study are commercially available sugars. However, since the objective of the study is to investigate their efficacy in preventing the onset of AD, the clinical study will be conducted as a specific clinical study in accordance with unapproved drugs. A summary of the foods to be used is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The information of test sugar and control sugar

Test sugar (kestose)

Type of drug, medical device, or regenerative medical product	Food
State of the approval	Off-label
Generic name	Kestose
Brand name	baby oligo® (Natural Science Co., Ltd.Tokyo,Japan)
Approval number	Not applicable to food

Route of administration, dosage, or duration of use	No restrictions on route of administration, dosage, or duration of use due to the type (i.e., food)
Target population (age group, sex, disease, etc.)	Safety confirmed for consumption from approximately 5 months of age, and the compound can be taken regardless of sex or disease status
Clinically significant findings on the efficacy and safety of the drug, etc., obtained from non-clinical studies, other clinical studies	The drug is highly effective in increasing the number of useful intestinal bacteria through oral intake, and is selectively utilized by useful bacteria, such as bifidobacteria and butyrate-producing bacteria
Benefits and disadvantages (known and potential) of drug administration, etc.	Benefits of administration include the possibility of improved intestinal health Disadvantages include the potential to cause transient diarrhea, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, bloating, flatulence, and belching

Control sugar (Maltose)

Type of drug, medical device, or regenerative medical product	Food
State of the approval	Off-label
Generic name	Maltose
Brand name	SUNMALT S® (Hayashibara Co., Ltd.Okayama,Japan)
Approval number	Not applicable to food
Route of administration, dosage, or duration of use	No restrictions on route of administration, dosage, or duration of use due to the type (i.e., food)
Target population (age group, sex, disease, etc.)	No restrictions due to the type (i.e., food)
Clinically significant findings on the efficacy and safety of the drug, etc., obtained from non-clinical studies, other clinical studies	When ingested orally, the drug has a limited effect on the large intestine because it is broken down by maltase in the intestinal fluid before being absorbed in the small intestine
Benefits and disadvantages (known and potential) of drug administration, etc.	No benefit is anticipated Disadvantages include the potential to cause transient diarrhea, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, bloating, flatulence, and belching

3. Purpose

The present double-blinded, randomized, and controlled trial will explore whether kestose intake is more effective than maltose intake in preventing the development of AD in high-risk newborns.

The primary endpoint will be the proportion of AD at 5 months (20 weeks) of age.

4. Matters related to the content of the study

4.1. Phase of the study

This is an exploratory phase II study assessing treatment efficacy.

4.2. Sample size

We plan to enroll a total of 100 participants in two groups: kestose group (n=50) and maltose group (n=50).

Based on previous studies on the prevention of AD with moisturizers and a cohort study at our institution, the incidence of AD in high-risk newborns treated with moisturizers alone or with oral kestose in addition to moisturizers is 45% and 15%, respectively. This sample size would ensure a detection power of 79.3%.

Total sample size = 60 (Kestose:Control = 30:30)		Proportion of AD in Control arm							
		15%	20%	25%	30%	35%	40%	45%	50%
Proportion of AD in Kestose arm	5%	9.3%	24.1%	43.6%	63.1%	78.8%	89.3%	95.3%	98.2%
	10%	3.0%	9.6%	21.3%	37.2%	54.5%	70.5%	83.0%	91.4%
	15%	-	3.7%	9.3%	19.2%	33.0%	48.9%	64.5%	77.7%
	20%	-	-	3.9%	8.9%	17.6%	29.8%	44.4%	59.6%
	25%	-	-	-	4.0%	8.4%	16.1%	27.2%	41.3%
	30%	-	-	-	-	3.9%	7.8%	15.0%	25.9%

Total sample size = 80 (Kestose:Control = 40:40)		Proportion of AD in Control arm							
		15%	20%	25%	30%	35%	40%	45%	50%
Proportion of AD in Kestose arm	5%	18.3%	41.1%	64.5%	82.1%	92.3%	97.3%	99.2%	99.8%
	10%	5.4%	16.2%	33.4%	53.4%	71.7%	85.2%	93.5%	97.6%
	15%	-	5.5%	13.9%	28.1%	45.9%	64.1%	79.3%	89.7%
	20%	-	-	5.2%	12.3%	24.5%	40.8%	58.6%	74.9%
	25%	-	-	-	4.9%	11.1%	22.1%	37.7%	55.9%
	30%	-	-	-	-	4.6%	10.5%	21.2%	36.8%

The number of births at our facility exceeds 2,000 per year; of those, approximately 1,200 are singleton vaginal deliveries at ≥37 weeks of gestation. According to epidemiological studies of AD, the prevalence of AD in adults is approximately 5%. Approximately 10% of high-risk newborns have one or two parents with AD. Assuming a consent rate of approximately 80%, we planned to recruit 100 newborns during the enrollment period (12 months).

4.3. Study design

This is a double-blinded, randomized, and controlled trial investigating the effect of kestose intake on the prevention of AD in neonates at high risk of developing the disease. A maltose group was set up as control; thus far, there is no evidence regarding the involvement of maltose in the prevention of AD. The flow of the clinical study is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4

Rationale: Kestose is expected to prevent AD by increasing the abundance of butyrate-producing bacteria in the gut and inducing regulatory T cell differentiation. However, there is no information on the magnitude of this effect; hence, an exploratory study is warranted. Randomization is also needed to compare the preventive effect on AD while ensuring comparability with the control group.

5. Eligibility

Individuals who meet all of the following selection criteria and who do not meet any of the exclusion criteria will be considered for inclusion in this study.

5.1. Inclusion criteria

- 1) Newborns within 6 days of the date of consent
- 2) Newborns with at least one parent or sibling who has a history of AD (i.e., high-risk newborns)
- 3) Neonates whose parent have been informed of the purpose of the study, fully understand the details of the study and provide written consent for their participation.

[Rationale] 1), 2) The purpose of this study is to evaluate the efficacy of early intervention in neonates at high risk of developing AD.

5.2. Exclusion criteria

- 1) Newborn infants who have already developed AD
- 2) Newborn infants receiving treatment with topical drugs, such as steroids (excluding mouth, genital and anal areas)

- 3) Newborn infants with skin lesions, such as abnormal keratinization and bullous disease
- 4) Newborn at <37 weeks of gestation
- 5) Newborn delivered by cesarean section
- 6) Presence of multiple fetuses
- 7) Newborn with serious complications
- 8) Planning to relocate during the study period and may not be able to visit the research facility
- 9) Unable to understand Japanese
- 10) In addition, if the investigator judges it inappropriate

[Rationale] criteria 1–6: Owing to concerns regarding the impact on efficacy evaluation; criteria 6–9: owing to concerns regarding the impact on safety or ethical considerations.

5.3. Discontinuation of treatment

The principal investigator or sub-investigator will discontinue the intake of kestose and maltose and the application of cosmetics if he/she determines that the study cannot be continued for any of the following reasons. The date and reason for discontinuation shall be recorded and noted in the medical record and electronic case report form(eCRF), and necessary tests shall be performed at the time of discontinuation to evaluate the efficacy and safety. In case of discontinuation due to outbreak of disease, follow-up should be conducted until the participant recovers to the current status as much as possible.

- 1) When AD is diagnosed
- 2) When consent is withdrawn by the participant's parents
- 3) If, after enrollment, the participant does not meet the selection criteria or violates the exclusion criteria
- 4) If the participant is unable to continue the study due to illness or other reasons
- 5) If the participant does not visit the hospital due to relocation, etc.
- 6) Other cases in which discontinuation of the study is deemed appropriate by the principal investigator or sub-investigator.

5.4. Discontinuation of the study

The investigator will consider whether or not to continue the study if any of the following apply. The study will be terminated if the Efficacy and Safety Evaluation Committee or the Accredited Clinical Research Review Committee recommends or instructs the investigators to discontinue the study. The principal investigator will submit a notice of discontinuation to the Authorized Clinical Research Review Committee within 10 days of the decision to discontinue the study early, as well as a notification of discontinuation of the specified clinical research to the Minister of Health, Labour and Welfare. The administrator of the site will be notified in writing of the discontinuation, including the reason for the discontinuation. The parents will be notified promptly to ensure the appropriate post-procedure for each participant.

- 1) When significant information regarding the quality, safety, or efficacy of kestose or maltose is obtained.
- 2) If it is determined that the recruitment of research participants is difficult, or in case of a high discontinuation rate that may complicate the completion of the study.
- 3) When the Efficacy and Safety Assessment Committee or the Accredited Clinical Research Review Committee

instructs the investigators to amend the research protocol, etc., and it is deemed difficult to perform such alterations.

6. Study procedures

6.1. Registration

The Electronic Data Capture (EDC) system will be used to enroll participants and conduct random assignment.

- 1) The principal investigator or sub-investigator will obtain written consent for participation in the study from the participant's parent the prescribed form and confirm that the candidate meets all the selection criteria after birth and does not violate any of the exclusion criteria.
- 2) The principal investigator or sub-investigator investigator will check the eligibility criteria for the candidates deemed eligible, confirm that all selection criteria are met and that all exclusion criteria are not violated, and input the participant and case registration information in the EDC system. If eligible, a participant identification number will be issued and a study meal number will be assigned.
- 3) If eligible, an enrollment confirmation notice will be automatically sent to the principal investigator, Affiliate Investigator, and data center via e-mail.
- 4) The principal investigator or sub-investigator will review the assignment results and perform the assigned study intervention.

Precautions for enrollment

- 1) Ineligible participants and participants who withdrew consent prior to enrollment will not be registered in the EDC system.
- 2) In case of incomplete information regarding the participant, registration will not be accepted until all fields are completed.
- 3) Registration is considered complete upon receipt of an e-mail notification confirming registration.
- 4) The data center should be notified promptly in the event of registration errors, duplicate registrations, withdrawal of consent, discontinuation, dropouts, etc.
- 5) In the event of a duplicate registration, the earlier registration shall take precedence.

6.2. Randomization and stratification

Participants will be assigned using a 1:1 ratio to the kestose or maltose group through the substitution block method in the order of enrollment. Allocation adjustment factors will not be used in this investigation.

6.3. Blinding

The participants, investigator, and principal investigator will be blinded regarding the interventions in this study. The details of blinding are separately stipulated in the "Procedures for Assignment of Test Meals."

6.4. Disclosure of allocation in case of emergency

If the study sub-investigator determines that information on the study intervention group is necessary, such as in the

case of a serious adverse event, the sub-investigator will inform the principal investigator of the need for emergency disclosure.

. If the principal investigator determines that allocation disclosure is necessary, he/she will submit a request to the Emergency Allocation Code Officer to disclose the allocation of the participant in question. The Emergency Allocation Code Administrator will open the allocation code for the participant for whom allocation disclosure has been requested and notify the principal investigator of the results. If the principal investigator makes an allocation disclosure, he/she will specify in the medical record the reason justifying the disclosure.

6.5. Study intervention

The intervention in this study will be initiated between neonatal discharge and 2 weeks of age (allowed up to 14 days of age + 3 days), but not during hospitalization. Thereafter, the study intervention period is defined as the period from the start date of intake of test and control sugars to 20 weeks of age (Visit 4) or until the date of discontinuation. Day 6 will typically be the neonatal discharge date; if discharge occurs before or after day 6, the reason will be recorded in the electronic medical record. Of note, there will be no exclusion or discontinuation criteria for participants due to the change in discharge date. The principal investigator or sub-investigator will instruct the parent or family members on the method of administration of the test or control sugar, application of cosmetics, and recording of the results in a paper diary before the neonate is discharged from the hospital. The test sugars, control sugars, and cosmetics will be delivered to the residences of the participants (or designated delivery addresses) by the time the participants reach 2 weeks of age. The principal investigator or a sub-investigator will review the logbook at each visit. If the child experiences obvious vomiting (except for a small amount of milk regurgitation) within 10 min of ingesting the test or control sugar, it is assumed that the child was unable to ingest the sugar on that occasion.

<Method and period of kestose and maltose intake>

(i) Kestose group

- In the neonatal period (i.e., from the start of the intervention to 30 days of age*), 0.3 g/dose thrice daily (0.9 g/day)
- From 31 days of age* to 20 weeks of age (i.e., until the assessment of the primary endpoint), 0.5 g/dose twice daily (1.0 g/day)

(ii) Maltose group

- In the neonatal period (from the start of the intervention to 30 days of age*), 0.3 g/dose thrice daily (0.9 g/day)
- From 31 days of age* to 20 weeks of age (until the assessment of the primary endpoint), 0.5 g/dose twice daily (1.0 g/day).

* Switching day for frequency and dose is allowed from 31 days of age + 7 days

Method of intake: Both kestose and maltose should be dissolved in a small amount of breast milk, formula, or plain hot water and ingested.

<Common items for the two groups>

- During the study intervention period, the provided cosmetics (Baby Milky Cream) shall be used at least once daily.
- The cleaning products (baby hair shampoo for the head and baby full-body shampoo for the face and body) shall be used once daily.
- During the study intervention period, the use of cosmetics other than those provided will be prohibited.
- The consumption of oligosaccharides and probiotic/prebiotic foods other than the test foods will also be prohibited.
- Topical corticosteroids and dermal products may be used during the study period under the direction of the study physician or another physician.
- Weaning (i.e., the consumption of foods other than formula or breast milk) will not be initiated until the evaluation of the primary endpoint in 20-week-old infants.

6.6. Study assessments

The day of birth is day 0, and the day of neonatal discharge will typically be day 6. If the study intervention is discontinued, data will be collected at that time for the end-of-study (i.e., 20 weeks of age) endpoints. In the event of discontinuation due to the occurrence of disease or other event, the participant will be followed up until recovery to the current status as much as possible.

Assessment schedule

	Study period				Unscheduled medical examination (At the time of appearance of skin rash ¹⁷⁾)	At the time of discontinuation of the study
Visit	1	2	3	4 (At the end of the study)		
Outpatients or inpatients	Inpatients (before discharge)	Outpatients	Outpatients	Outpatients	Outpatients (Temporary)	Outpatients (Temporary)
Time point (Visit windows)	Entry	4 weeks after birth (+/- 14 days)	12 weeks after birth (+/- 14 days)	20 weeks after birth (+/- 14 days)		

Entry	X					
Informed consent	X					
Allocation	X					
Background information ¹⁾	X					
Living environment ²⁾	X			X		X
Nutrition ³⁾	X			X		X
Complications/ past medical history	X					
Ingestion of test sugar		X	X	X	X	X
Body height	X	X	X	X	X	X
Body weight	X	X	X	X	X	X
AD ⁴⁾		X	X	X	X	X
EASI ⁵⁾		X	X	X	X	X
POEM ⁶⁾		X	X	X	X	X
SCH ⁷⁾	X	X	X	X		X
TEWL ⁸⁾	X	X	X	X		X
Wheezing ⁹⁾				X		X
Food allergy ¹⁰⁾				X		X
Blood test ¹¹⁾				X		X
Fecal examination ¹²⁾	X	X	X	X		X
Information on bowel movements ¹³⁾	X	X	X	X		X
Review of logbook ¹⁴⁾		X	X	X	X	X
Amount of cosmetics used ¹⁵⁾		X	X	X		X
Concomitant therapy ¹⁶⁾	X	X	X	X	X	X

Adverse event		X	X	X	X	X
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Details of survey items

- 1) Participant and family background: information will be collected from questionnaires and electronic medical records.
 - Participant background: sex, date of birth, weeks of gestation, birth height, birth weight, mode of delivery, history of complications/previous medical history, race
 - Background of participant's mother: age at enrolment, educational background, history of allergic disease, information on antimicrobial use during pregnancy, duration of administration
 - Background of participant's father: educational background, history of allergic disease
 - Background of participant's siblings: number of siblings, history of allergic disease
- 2) Living environment: information will be collected through a questionnaire; pets (dogs, cats, others) in the main residence, smoking in the family.
- 3) Nutritional intake: information will be collected through a questionnaire. Information on breast milk intake, general formula intake and its product name, hydrolyzed formula intake and its product name, whether or not weaning has been initiated and the initiation date, whether or not eggs/milk (dairy products other than formula)/wheat/soy/peanut products are consumed and the start date, intake of oligosaccharides and probiotics/prebiotics other than test foods, and the presence/absence and number of days of intake of foods other than the study foods (i.e., other oligosaccharides and probiotics/prebiotics).
- 4) Diagnostic criteria for AD: the diagnostic criteria established by the United Kingdom Working Party are used in this study (see Table 2); the criteria for AD were developed by Williams et al. and consist of one major criterion and five minor criteria. Diagnosis of AD is reached when a research physician deems that the patient fulfilled the major criterion and at least three of the minor criteria.

Table 2. Diagnostic criteria of the United Kingdom Working Party

Major criterion
Presence of an itchy skin condition (or parental report of scratching or rubbing in a child)
Minor criteria
History of involvement of the skin creases, such as folds of elbows, behind the knees, front of ankles, or around the neck (including cheeks in children aged < 10 years)
A personal history of asthma or hay fever (or history of atopic disease in a first-degree relative of children aged <4)
A personal history of general dry skin in the last 12 months
Presence of visible flexural eczema (or eczema involving the cheeks/forehead and outer limbs in children aged <4)
Onset in children aged < 2 years (not used if the child is aged < 4 years)

- 5) Eczema Area and Severity Index (EASI): the EASI score, developed by Hanifin et al., is a tool used to measure the

extent (area) and severity of atopic eczema 2). It is assessed only at the time of diagnosis of AD.

- 6) Participant-Oriented Eczema Measure (POEM): the POEM score, developed by Williams et al., is a tool used to measure the severity of AD by participants (caregivers). It is assessed only at the time of diagnosis of AD using a questionnaire.
- 7) Stratum corneum hydration (SCH): the amount of water in the stratum corneum, which is an indicator of skin hydration. The principal investigator or a sub-investigator will take five measurements at the forehead (5 cm above the midpoint of both eyes) and at the outer lower leg (midpoint of the central and outer patella) using a Corneometer® (Courage+Khazaka electronic GmbH, Cologne, Germany) and record the three values except minimum and maximum.
- 8) Transdermal water loss (TEWL): the amount of water that evaporates from the skin, which is an indicator of skin barrier function. The principal investigator or a sub-investigator will take three measurements at the forehead (5 cm above the midpoint of both eyes) and at the outer lower leg (midpoint of the central and outer patella) using a VAPOMETER® (Delfin Technologies Ltd, Kuopio, Finland) and record the data.
- 9) Expiratory wheezing: according to a medical history taken by the principal investigator or a sub-investigator.
- 10) Presence/absence of food allergy: according to the medical history taken by the principal investigator or a sub-investigator.
- 11) Blood tests: total IgE antibody titer, specific IgE antibody titer (milk, egg white, ovomucoid, wheat, peanut, Kona leopard mite) and serum squamous cell carcinoma antigen 2 (SCCA2) levels will be measured. Total and specific IgE antibody titers will be measured using the ImmunoCAP® (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Massachusetts, USA) method. Whole blood (3 ml) will be collected and measured at the laboratory center in the implementing medical center; thereafter, the residual blood (serum) will be frozen and stored at the sample storage center in the allergy center. In addition, the abundance of regulatory T cells will be measured in 20-week-old participants at visit 4. In these cases, larger whole blood samples (approximately 6 ml) will be collected.
- 12) Fecal examination: fecal samples will be collected and analyzed for intestinal microbiota by next-generation sequencing to provide an indicator of the intestinal environment. For the examination of intestinal bacteria, feces will be collected with an intestinal bacteria kit (manufactured by Healthcare System Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) and sent to an institute for analysis of the intestinal microflora at room temperature.
- 13) Simultaneously with the fecal examination, information will be collected using a questionnaire related to defecation (stool characteristics, intake of pre-probiotics other than the test sugar, frequency of defecation, number of days of defecation, stool color, etc.).
- 14) The paper diary should include the status of kestose or maltose intake, i.e., number of missed administrations, reason (optional: (i) forgotten intake; (ii) vomiting within 10 min of intake; (iii) refusal of child to receive the treatment; (iv) other [free entry]), application of the cosmetics provided, use and type of other cosmetics, and presence of skin rash.
- 15) The amount of remaining cosmetic (baby milky cream) will be measured.
- 16) The presence/absence, name, duration, and site of application of topical skin medications (steroids, other anti-inflammatory topicals), oral or transvenous antibiotics, oral or transvenous steroids/immunosuppressants, skin moisturizers/general ointment bases/cosmetics (other than those provided by Natural Science Co., Ltd.) (general,

head, face, trunk [including neck, ears]) will be recorded. The investigator or a sub-investigator will review the diary, medical history and medication diary for the presence, name, duration, application site (whole body, head, face, trunk [including neck, ears, and buttocks], extremities, perioral area, perineum/perianal area, other) and purpose of use.

17) Treatment of skin rashes during the study period will be carried out in the hospital. The principal investigator or sub-investigator physician will diagnose AD, decide whether the study needs to be suspended or discontinued, and initiate treatment for the skin rash if necessary.

7. Efficacy endpoints

7.1. Primary endpoint

Proportion of participants with AD aged ≤ 20 weeks

[Rationale] This study explores the prevention of AD onset by kestose. Kestose is commonly found in foods; this fact may lead to variations in individual intake beyond the intervention following the initiation of weaning. It is also difficult to determine the exact amount of kestose contained in the weaning food consumed. Therefore, the primary endpoint will be the proportion of children aged ≤ 20 weeks who develop AD before the initiation of weaning.

7.2. Secondary endpoints

- 1) Disease-free days of AD
- 2) EASI score at the diagnosis of AD
- 3) POEM score at the diagnosis of AD
- 4) SCH, TEWL
- 5) Proportion of expiratory wheeze ≤ 20 weeks of age
- 6) Proportion of food allergies as judged by a physician ≤ 20 weeks of age
- 7) Total IgE antibody titer, specific IgE antibody titer
- 8) Regulatory T cell abundance
- 9) Serum SCCA2 levels
- 10) Intestinal microflora examination by fecal collection
- 11) Fecal properties and defecation status

8. Safety assessment

8.1. Safety endpoints

All adverse events occurring during the study intervention period (from the start date of intake of test and control sugars to the visit at 20 weeks of age or AD diagnosis) will be investigated in this study. The principal investigator and sub-investigator will input the following items in the EDC system. The onset of AD is not included in the investigation of adverse events.

- (1) Event name;
- (2) Date of onset;

- (3) Severity (mild, moderate, and severe);
- (4) Seriousness (serious, non-serious);
- (5) Intervention measures (continuation, interruption, and discontinuation);
- (6) Measures [none, yes (contents if yes)];
- (7) Outcomes (recovery, remission, unrecovered, recovered but with sequelae, death, and unknown) and outcome confirmation date;
- 8) Causal relationship with the intake of kestose or maltose (can be denied, cannot be denied) ;

8.2. Reporting of illness and response to serious illness

Kestose and maltose used in this study may cause diarrhea, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, bloating, flatulence, and belching. As both are food products, it is unlikely that serious illnesses, etc. resulting from the interventions will occur. However, in case serious illnesses, etc. do occur, they will be managed in accordance with the “Procedures for reporting illnesses, etc.” If treatment for a disease or illness resulting from the intervention is continued after the intervention period, the observation period will be extended until the investigator decides that observation is no longer necessary from the perspective of ensuring the safety of the participant.

The term “illness, etc.” refers to any illness, disability, infection (including abnormal laboratory values and symptoms), or death suspected to be the result of the intervention (i.e., any adverse event for which a causal relationship with the study intervention cannot be ruled out). In addition, “serious illness, etc.” indicates any of the following:

- (i) Death
- (ii) Illness, etc. that may lead to death
- (iii) Illness, etc. requiring hospitalization or prolonged hospitalization in a medical institution for treatment
- (iv) Disability
- (v) Illness, etc. that may lead to disability
- (vi) Diseases, etc., which are as serious as (iii) to (v) above and death and diseases, etc., which may lead to death
- (vii) Congenital diseases or abnormalities in subsequent generations

9. Statistical analyses

9.1. Analysis set

The following data sets will be used for the analysis. Analyses of the primary and secondary endpoints will be conducted on the largest analysis population. As a reference, analyses will be conducted on the target population that conforms to the research protocol. The analysis of safety endpoints shall be conducted on the target population of the safety analysis. In the event of a serious violation, such as a violation of obtaining consent, the participant concerned will be excluded from all analysis target populations.

(1) Largest analysis population: Full Analysis Set

The population of all participants for whom randomization has been performed, excluding participants:

- who have never undergone any study intervention

- for whom no data were available following the initiation of the study intervention
- who are subsequently found to have violated the eligibility criteria.

(2) Analysis population conforming to the study protocol: Per Protocol Set

A population consisting of participants in the Full Analysis Set with no serious deviations from the protocol.

- Poor adherence. Intake of kestose or maltose for $\geq 70\%$ or $< 70\%$ of the study intervention period days denotes good and poor adherence, respectively. The number of days of intake is calculated based on the number of days in which intake took place at least once.
- If adherence cannot be assessed.
- If weaning was initiated before the end of the assessment of the primary endpoint at 20 weeks of age.
- If oligosaccharides or pre-probiotic foods other than the study food were consumed for > 7 days during the study period.

(3) Safety analysis population: Safety Population (SP)

Population consisting of all participants in whom the study intervention has been performed at least once.

9.2. Significance level

When testing the primary and secondary endpoints, the significance level will be set at 5%.

9.3. Analysis methods

Details of the analysis methods will be described in a separate statistical analysis plan, which will be defined prior to case fixation.

9.3.1. Summary of background information

The following summary statistics will be calculated for each group of participants. For discrete data (e.g., sex, family history), the frequency and percentage (%) of each category will be calculated; for continuous data (e.g., age in days or months, height, weight), the mean, standard deviation, median, interquartile range, and minimum and maximum values will be calculated.

9.3.2. Analysis of primary endpoints

Analyses will be performed according to the Intention-to-Treat (ITT) principle. For each treatment group, the proportion of children aged ≤ 20 weeks with or without AD and the corresponding 95% CI will be calculated. The 95% CI for the proportions will be calculated using the Clopper–Pearson method.

To evaluate the research hypothesis “that the kestose group is more effective in preventing the onset of AD compared with the maltose group,” the null hypothesis is that “the proportion of AD among participants aged ≤ 20 weeks in the kestose and maltose groups are equal.” Moreover, the two-tailed hypothesis test with the alternative hypothesis is that “the proportion of AD among participants aged ≤ 20 weeks in the kestose and maltose groups is different.” A Fisher’s exact probability test will be performed to calculate the *P*-value for the occurrence of AD within 20 weeks of age in the

kestose and maltose groups. The significance level will be set at 5.0%.

9.3.3. Analysis of secondary endpoints

Analyses will be conducted according to the ITT principle. Details of the analysis methods will be described in a separate statistical analysis plan, which will be defined prior to case fixation.

9.3.4. Analysis of safety endpoints

Analyses will be conducted according to the ITT principle. Details of the analysis methods will be described in a separate statistical analysis plan, which will be defined prior to case fixation.

9.4. Interim analysis

Interim analyses will not be carried out.

9.5. Procedure for modifying the statistical analysis plan

Before data fixation, additions and changes to the statistical analysis plan may be performed, as necessary. If changes are made to the analysis plan described in the research protocol, they should also be explained in the analysis plan and the summary report of the clinical study. The amendments and the reason responsible for the changes should also be explained in the analysis plan and the summary report of the clinical study.

10. Access to original documents and other materials

10.1. Scope of source documents

Source documents in this study shall include medical records, laboratory data, and logbooks.

10.2. Guarantee of direct access to source documents

Principal investigators, sub-investigators, and the implementing healthcare organization shall ensure that all clinical research-related records, including source documents, are available for direct inspection during monitoring by accredited clinical research review committees, as well as investigations by regulatory authorities and other authorities related to the study. Principal investigators, sub-investigators, and the implementing healthcare organization shall cooperate with these bodies for such matters.

11. Quality control and quality assurance

11.1. Monitoring

On-site monitoring will be performed to ensure that the study is conducted safely and in accordance with the study protocol, and that data are accurately collected. Monitoring will be carried out by an individual nominated by the principal investigator in accordance with the Monitoring Procedures and Plan, which will be specified separately.

11.2. Audit

Audits will not be conducted.

11.3. Effectiveness and safety evaluation committee

The Effectiveness and Safety Assessment Committee will meet when any of the following assessment items are obtained and will make recommendations to the principal investigator regarding the continuation, modification, or discontinuation of the study.

- 1) Significant changes to the research protocol
- 2) Occurrence of serious diseases, etc.
- 3) Identification of serious problems in monitoring, etc.
- 4) Other cases where the principal investigator considers that deliberation by the Effectiveness and Safety Assessment Committee is necessary.

12. Ethical considerations

12.1. Rules to be observed

Before conducting the research, all individuals involved in the study shall read, understand, and comply with the contents of the Declaration of Helsinki of the World Medical Association and the Clinical Research Act. All medical research involving human participants must comply with the tenets of this declaration. Prior to the commencement of the study, the principal investigator shall obtain the opinion of an accredited clinical research review committee on the conduct of the study, obtain approval from the administrator of the implementing medical institution, and submit an implementation plan to the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare (Japan).

12.2. Handling of personal information

Individuals involved in the implementation of the study shall give due consideration to the protection of the privacy and personal information of the participants. During the study, the principal investigator shall establish the necessary safety control measures and systems for the protection of personal information. A joint research agreement has been concluded with Natural Science Co., Ltd., and confidentiality obligations have been imposed. The names and addresses of individual participants will be provided to Natural Science Co., Ltd. for the delivery of test meals, cosmetics, and cleaning products. Consent will be obtained by explaining in writing that personal information will not be used for any other purpose.

The principal investigator will assign a unique anonymized number (participant identification number) to the participant and manage the data and samples in such a manner that prevents the identification of individuals. The participant identification number will be used to identify individuals between the research office and data center. Participant identification numbers and participant identities will be appropriately managed by the personal information manager designated by the implementing medical institution using a personal information correspondence table. This information will not be communicated to the data center or the individual responsible for statistical analysis.

Participant-identifying information will not be used when the results of the study are published. Individuals involved in the conduct of the study will not divulge to third party information related to the identity of participants, which is obtained through access to the source documents. If participant data and samples obtained in this study are to be used for purposes other than those of this study, consent will be separately obtained from the participant's parent, as necessary.

If participant data and samples obtained in this study are to be used for future research, a separate research protocol will be prepared and a new application for approval will be submitted to an accredited clinical research review committee or an ethics review committee, and the data and samples will be used appropriately.

12.3. Measures to minimize the benefits and burdens and anticipated risks to the participants

The benefits to participants in this study include the possibility of preventing the onset of AD through the intake of kestose from the early post-natal period. Disadvantages include the time and effort required for participants to consume kestose or maltose daily, the time and effort required for the application of cosmetics, and the burden of filling in diaries and questionnaires on behalf of the participants. In addition, stomach discomfort, diarrhea, and abdominal pain may occur due to the ingestion of kestose or maltose. However, all of the items used in the study are foodstuffs; thus, it is unlikely that intake of these sugars will lead to the occurrence of serious illnesses or other problems. In the event of serious illness, etc., in participants in this study for which a causal relationship with kestose or maltose cannot be denied, the principal investigators and sub-investigators will promptly discontinue the study intervention, take necessary measures (e.g., treatment), and strive to ensure the safety of the participants and the optimal implementation of treatment.

13. Handling and storage of records

13.1. Handling and storage of documents

The principal investigator shall retain the following documents relating to the conduct of the study, etc., for 5 years from the date of completion of the entire study.

- 1) Research protocols, implementation plans, documents pertaining to explanations to participants of specific clinical research and their consent, summary reports and other documents or copies thereof prepared by the principal investigator in accordance with the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare Ordinance under Article 12 of the Act
- 2) Documents received from accredited clinical research review committees pertaining to review opinion work
- 3) Documents related to monitoring
- 4) Original documents, etc.
- 5) Contracts pertaining to the implementation of the specified clinical research
- 6) Documents containing an outline of the medicinal products, etc., to be used in the specified clinical research and records relating to the medicinal products, etc.
- 7) Other documents necessary for conducting the specified clinical research

13.2. Storage of samples, etc., and use of samples, etc., by other institutions, etc.

The principal investigator shall properly store the samples, etc. of the participants obtained in the study until at least 5 years have elapsed from the date of study completion. All remaining samples examined at the testing center shall be destroyed by appropriate means. If the remaining samples are to be used for future research not identified at the time consent is received, this will be performed after separate explanation has been provided to the research participant and consent has been obtained .

13.3. Data collection methods

Data relating to the study will be collected in a data format that does not contain personally identifiable information using the EDC system. Principal investigators and sub-investigators will promptly input data into the EDC system after each visit. The participant's parent will record the data in a logbook.

14. Payment of money and compensation for the conduct of clinical research

14.1. Funding sources and financial offices (matters relating to conflicts of interest)

The study will be conducted as a collaborative study using funds provided by Natural Science Co., Ltd. This company will be involved in part of the implementation of the research (i.e., provision of test sugar, control sugar, and cosmetics to the participants) and in the preparation of presentation materials based on the findings (i.e., cooperation in the preparation of articles, materials for conferences, etc.). Nevertheless, it will not be involved in the analysis of the results. The state of conflict of interest due to joint research will not affect the planning and implementation of the study, as well as the results and interpretation of the study. Furthermore, implementation of the study will not damage the rights and interests of the participants. Regarding the management of conflicts of interest in relation to the aforementioned company, the principal investigator has submitted a conflict of interest management standard and a conflict of interest management plan to an accredited clinical research review committee for approval. This process was performed in accordance with the guidance on conflict of interest management for clinical research in the Clinical Research Act. Each researcher shall appropriately manage conflicts of interest related to the study in accordance with the Conflict of Interest Management Standards and the Conflict of Interest Management Plan. The researchers will appropriately disclose these data upon request by academic societies and medical journals, in which the research results may be published.

14.2. Cost related to the research

Kestose, maltose, cosmetics, and cleaning agents in this study will be provided by Natural Science Co., Ltd. The costs for the tests (keratin water content measurement, TEWL measurement, blood tests such as IgE antibody, stool tests) will be covered by funds provided by Natural Science Co., Ltd. All tests and drug prescriptions within the scope of normal medical care will be carried out through the insurance scheme (the 1-month check-up will be self-funded), and the expenses will be covered by the health insurance of the participant or co-payment. Therefore, there will be no additional cost incurred for the participants or their parent in this study.

In order to reduce the burden associated with participation in clinical research, a Quo card worth JPY 2,000 will be provided to participants per visit except visit 1, which is performed during hospitalization, as a participation cooperation fee at the end of the study intervention or at the time of discontinuation (excluding discontinuation caused by the participant, such as not visiting the hospital).

14.3. Compensation for damage to health

Treatment of any health damage arising from the study will be carried out to the best of the ability using the participant's health insurance, in the same manner as for normal medical treatment. All individuals involved in this study, including the principal investigator and the sub-investigator physicians, will be insured by clinical research insurance for compensation in case of damage to health. This insurance will cover damages incurred by the insured individual

assuming indemnity or legal liability in the event of damage to the health of participants (i.e., death, or level 1–2 disability according to the criteria of the Adverse Drug Reactions Relief System) participants a result of the clinical research.

15. Publication policy and attribution of productions

Prior to the initiation of the trial, the investigation will be registered in the database (jRCT) maintained by the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare. The results of the study shall belong to the National Centre for Child Health and Development and Natural Science Co., Ltd. The main study results will be submitted to a scientific journal for publication after completion of the final analysis. In principle, the first author of the main article of the study results will be determined by the research secretariat. Co-authors will be determined by the research office in accordance with the Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. All co-authors should review the content of the article prior to submission and agree on the content of the publication. Disagreements regarding the content will be discussed and, if an agreement cannot be reached, the research office may decide to exclude researchers from the co-author list.

16. Duration of clinical research

Case enrolment period: from the date of publication of the clinical study in the jRCT until September 30, 2024.

Total study period: from the date of publication of the clinical study in jRCT to September 30, 2026.

If the implementation period is extended for reasons such as failure to reach the target number of cases within the study implementation period, the extension will be participant to approval by the Authorized Clinical Research Review Committee.

17. Explanation to and consent of clinical research participants

17.1. Preparation and revision of explanatory documents and consent forms

Explanatory documents and consent forms will be prepared by the principal investigator and used after approval by an accredited clinical research review committee. If revisions are required, the revised application will be resubmitted to an accredited clinical research review committee for approval before use. The principal investigator will promptly revise the explanatory document when information is obtained that may influence the willingness of the participant's parent to continue participating in the research.

17.2. Informed consent

The study will be conducted after it has been reviewed and approved by an accredited clinical research review committee and published in the jRCT. Prior to the commencement of the study, the principal investigator and sub-investigator physicians shall clearly explain the study objectives to the participant's parent based on an explanatory document that includes the following items. After understanding the purpose and details of this investigation, the parent will provide free and voluntary consent in writing for participation in the study. The investigators will also explain that refusal to participate in this study will not have any consequences for the participant.

When obtaining consent, the investigators should offer sufficient time and opportunities to the participant's parent to

request information regarding participation in the study, and provide answers to any questions. If consent is obtained, the participant's parent, and the principal investigator or a sub-investigator should sign and date the consent form. A copy of the consent form and the explanatory document should be given to the participant, while the original consent form should be kept at the operating institution. The participants should also be informed that they have the right to withdraw consent at any time, and that withdrawal will not have any consequences.

In case the principal investigator or sub-investigator obtains new important information on the safety of kestose, maltose, or cosmetics, or if important information is obtained that may influence the willingness of participant's parent to consent, the parent should be promptly informed, and his/her willingness to continue the study should be confirmed. The principal investigator or the sub-investigator should record the date of explanation, the explainer, the content of the explanation, the willingness to continue, and the date of confirmation in the medical record or other documentation.

Explanatory notes

- 1) The name of the specific clinical research to be conducted, the fact that approval has been obtained from the administrator of the medical institution for the conduct of the specific clinical research, and that the implementation plan has been submitted to the Minister of Health, Labour and Welfare, the name of the research institution, and the name and title of the principal investigator
- 2) Purpose and significance of the research
- 3) Methods of the research
- 4) Reasons for selection as participants
- 5) Burdens to the participants and the anticipated benefits and disadvantages
- 6) Voluntary refusal to participate in the research
- 7) The right to withdraw consent
- 8) Handling of non-consent or withdrawal of consent
- 9) The fact that the research protocol and other documents relating to the conduct of the specified clinical research may be obtained or inspected at the request of the participants or their representatives, and the method used to obtain or inspect such documents
- 10) Financial burdens or rewards for participants
- 11) Existence and details of other treatment methods and comparison with the expected benefits and disadvantages of other treatment methods
- 12) Matters relating to compensation for damage to health and provision of medical care
- 13) Methods for the disclosure of information
- 14) Handling of personal information
- 15) Matters to be examined by the Authorized Clinical Research Review Committee, which is responsible for reviewing and providing an opinion on the specified clinical research, and other matters relating to the Authorized Clinical Research Review Committee for the specified clinical research in terms of methods for the storage and disposal of samples and information
- 16) Samples and information to be used for future research

17) Sources of research funding and status regarding conflicts of interest

18) Monitoring

19) Response to complaints and enquiries from participants and others

17.3. Informed assent

Informed assent will not be provided as the participants of this study are neonates.

17.4. Withdrawal of consent

The following actions will be taken in case the participant's parent expresses the desire to withdraw consent for participation in the study. The principal investigator confirms in writing the withdrawal of consent to research participation by the participant's parent using the withdrawal of consent form. The withdrawal of consent is set out as withdrawal of participation consent and withdrawal of full consent. The physician confirms in writing whether the withdrawal of consent is a withdrawal of participation only, in which case the data up to the point of withdrawal are not deleted and can be used for analysis. Alternatively, in case of full withdrawal of consent, participation in the study is discontinued and use of the data is prohibited. In both types of withdrawal, personal data (name and address) stored at Natural Science Co., Ltd. and the Clinical Research Center will be deleted at the time of withdrawal.

In case of withdrawal of consent for participation, the principal investigator will ask the research office to withdraw consent for participation in the study and destroy the residual sample. The research office will request the destruction of residual blood (serum) samples in the sample storage center and inform the research office using a prescribed form.

In case of withdrawal of full consent, the principal investigator will ask the research office to withdraw consent for participation in the study and destroy the relevant data. The research office will request the destruction of the relevant participant's data and samples in the data center and sample storage center. The data center will exclude the participant's data from the analysis data set, while the sample storage center will destroy the residual blood (serum) samples and inform the research office using a prescribed form..

18. Other matters necessary for the proper implementation of clinical research

18.1. Contents and methods of reporting to the administrator of the IMPLEMENTING medical institution

18.1.1. Reports from researchers, etc.

The researcher, etc., reports to the administrator of the implementing healthcare institution in the following cases.

- 1) When serious concerns arise from the perspective of respecting the human rights of research participants, etc., or from the perspective of conducting research, such as the leakage of information related to the research.
- 2) If facts or information that undermine or may undermine the appropriateness of the conduct of the research or the confidence in the results of the research are obtained.

18.1.2. Reports from the principal investigator

The principal investigator reports to the administrator of the implementing medical institution in the following cases.

- 1) After consulting an accredited clinical research review committee, he/she must submit the documents submitted to the review committee and other documents required by the administrator of the implementing medical institution. Moreover, he/she must obtain approval from the administrator to conduct the specified clinical research.
- 2) When the implementation plan is submitted, it must be promptly distributed to the administrator of the implementing medical institution.
- 3) When the investigators become aware that the clinical research is not in conformity with the Ministerial Ordinance or the research protocol ('non-conformity'), they must promptly inform the administrator of the implementing medical institution. If a non-conformity is found to be particularly serious, the opinion of the accredited clinical research review committee must be promptly obtained.
- 4) When the accredited clinical research review committee provides a response, a relevant report must be promptly distributed to the administrator of the implementing medical institution.
- 5) When the occurrence of a disease, etc. is related to the implementation of specified clinical research, this information must be reported to the administrator of the implementing medical institution within the specified period of time and, subsequently, to the accredited clinical research review committee.
- 6) The implementation status of the specified clinical research must be reported to the administrator of the implementing medical institution and, subsequently, to the Authorized Clinical Research Review Committee every year starting from the date on which the implementation plan was submitted to the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare (within eight weeks after the expiry of the relevant period).
- 7) When a primary endpoint report and a summary report are prepared, they must be submitted to the administrator of the implementing medical institution without delay, and a summary of those reports must be published. Furthermore, the publication of these summaries shall be promptly reported to the administrator of the implementing medical institution.

18.1.3. Report from the individual in charge of the audit

Audits will not be conducted in this study.

18.2. Changes to research protocols

Changes to the research protocol are handled separately as amendments and revisions. In case of changes to the content of the research protocol, the principal investigator will report these alterations to an accredited clinical research review committee and the Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare.

18.2.1. Amendments to the research protocol

- 1) May increase the risk to participants in the study
- 2) Substantially affect the study's primary endpoint
- 3) Substantially affect the study's conduct framework

A partial change to the research protocol that falls under one or more of the above is defined as an amendment. Version number upgrades of the Research Protocol and the Explanatory Consent Document due to amendments are indicated

to the nearest 1, such as 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 ... Following approval of the changes to the research protocol by the accredited clinical research review committee, a notification regarding changes to the implementation plan should be submitted to the regional health authorities. Importantly, the date of approval by the accredited clinical research review committee should be indicated on the cover page of the research protocol. Following approval by the accredited clinical research review committee, permission will be obtained from the administrator of the implementing medical institution for the details of the amendment. If approval is granted, the principal investigator will send a copy of the approval letter to the research office and take effect the changes to the research protocol (the principal investigator decides whether to suspend participant enrolment during this period). The actual effective date will be announced by the research office. After the effective date, the study will be conducted in accordance with the amendments approved by the accredited clinical research review committee. Until the effective date, the intervention and evaluation of enrolled participants will be conducted in accordance with the version of the research protocol before the amendment. However, if the safety of the participants is threatened by the content of the study protocol before the amendment, such as inadequate criteria for changing the intervention, deviations from the research protocol to ensure the safety of the participants during the intervention are acceptable.

18.2.2. Revisions to the research protocol

- 1) Is not likely to increase the risk to participants in the study
- 2) Does not substantially affect the primary endpoint of the study
- 3) Does not substantially affect the conduct framework of the study

A revision is defined as a change to the study protocol that meets all of the above. This includes changes to the research protocol due to errors or changes relating to site-specific information, changes relating to site-specific information that do not involve changes to the research protocol, and changes relating to conflicts of interest. In principle, participant registration will not be temporarily suspended in the event of a revision. Version numbers of the research protocol and the explanatory consent document are upgraded to one decimal place, e.g., 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, Following approval of the changes to the research protocol by the clinical research review committee, a notification regarding changes to the implementation plan should be submitted to the regional health authorities. Importantly, the date of approval by the approved clinical research review committee should be noted on the cover page of the research protocol. The effective date of changes to the research protocol is 2 weeks after the date of approval by the accredited clinical research review committee, unless there are special circumstances. The effective date is the date after the submission of the notification regarding changes to the implementation plan to the regional health authorities. The actual effective date will be announced by the research office. After the effective date, the study will be conducted in accordance with the revisions approved by the accredited clinical research review committee. If changes affect the format of the eCRF, the principal investigator will request a change of format by the Data Management Officer.

18.2.3. Explanation to participants and provision of consent following changes to the research protocol

If the research protocol is changed, the principal investigator will also change the explanatory documents targeting the research participants accordingly. The accredited clinical research review committee may deem that a written

explanation and provision of consent by the participant is necessary. In such cases, written consent will be obtained again.

18.3. Consultation

The research secretariat will act as a consultation service for complaints and enquiries regarding the clinical research from research participants and related parties.

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18.4. References

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18.5. Attachments

- 1) List of participating physicians
- 2) Procedures for distribution of test meals
- 3) Procedures for allocation of test meals
- 4) Procedures for reporting illnesses, etc.
- 5) Monitoring procedures and plans